

MAKING AN ECONOMIC CASE FOR INVESTING IN OUTDOOR AND INDOOR LIGHTING INTERVENTIONS

POLICY BRIEF

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The ENLIGHTENme project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 945238.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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CREDITS

This policy is part of an outreach research developed in the framework of ENLIGHTENme. It has been authored by Assoc. Prof. David McDaid (LSE).

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HIGHLIGHTS

- **Many costs of not taking action:** Poor light exposure is associated with multiple adverse impacts such as increased risks of depression, problems sleeping and accidents. Inappropriate outdoor lighting may also, for example, make locations less appealing, reducing the sense of community and intergenerational connections. All of these adverse impacts can have substantial economic costs.
- **Use economic arguments to make case for lighting interventions:** In health and other sectors economic evidence is routinely required for policy decisions. This evidence can be critical to funding decisions.
- **Multiple benefits:** In making an economic case for lighting interventions it is important to measure impacts of most relevance to potential funders. For indoor lighting, health outcomes and service use are critical. For outdoor lighting, impacts such as neighbourhood footfall or perceptions of crime risk, may be even more relevant
- **Recommendations:** Increase awareness of the economic costs of poor light exposure; quantify the resources and costs to deliver lighting interventions; ensure evaluation includes assessment of economic costs and benefits of lighting interventions, looking at outcomes that are of key importance to the relevant decision makers.

AIM

This policy brief aims to provide an overview of why it is important to take account of economic impacts when making a case to policy makers to invest in indoor and outdoor lighting interventions. It describes key economic questions to address and provides some examples of potential economic impacts of poor lighting that could be averted through investment in effective lighting interventions. It also sets out what key issues to consider when making an economic case to policy makers working in different sectors.

BACKGROUND

The importance of good light exposure is not typically highlighted as a major public health or broader economic priority. This is despite the mounting evidence that the quality of light around us at different times of day and night can have a profound impact on our health and wellbeing. One of the reasons for the relatively low level of priority given to lighting may be because there is limited awareness of potential adverse economic impacts of poor lighting. There **appear to be very few cost effectiveness studies that have looked at the case for good lighting**, particular as an intervention to improve and protect health and wellbeing. We can take the light around us for granted, but poor light exposure is associated with multiple adverse impacts within and beyond health systems, all of which have economic costs. For example, there may be increased risks of depression and anxiety disorders, poor wellbeing, as well as problems sleeping. This is in addition to the association between poor lighting and risk of injuries such as falls, especially in older people whose vision may be deteriorating. When considering outdoor lighting there are many additional broad impacts to consider. Lighting can influence whether or not a location is seen as appealing. For example, potentially areas with poor lighting might be perceived by some older people as being less safe to be in. This perception may align with a lower sense of community, and reduce opportunities for intergenerational connections. Intergenerational and other connections can be vital to reducing the risk of enduring loneliness. These are just a few examples of the some of the adverse outcomes for which poor lighting can be a risk factor. Critically all of these adverse impacts can have substantial economic costs, some of which could be avoided through the use of effective lighting interventions. Identifying these impacts can help strengthen the case for investing in good light. For instance, there are many different health and wider economic impacts of insomnia and other sleep disorders. Poor sleep is associated with higher risk of mortality and onset of many chronic health conditions, including heart disease, diabetes and depression. Poor sleep impairs wellbeing, productivity at work and cognitive abilities. The annual economic costs of poor sleep have been estimated at almost 2% of economic output (GDP) in both Germany and the UK. If poor lighting hampers social connections it may also increase the risk of loneliness; this also has substantial costs due to increased risks of poor mental and physical health. In Spain the annual costs of loneliness for the population have been estimated to be more than 1.2% of GDP (€14 billion in 2021), and work in England indicates that modest reductions in loneliness through better community engagement can be cost effective. Therefore, **if investment in effective lighting interventions can reduce even just a small fraction of these costs, they are likely to be very cost effective.**

RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the lack of economic evidence, a number of interlinked steps that can be used to strengthen the economic case for investing in lighting interventions is set out. This is needed because economic evidence is routinely used as one piece of information in making policy decisions. In the case of health systems, formal assessment of cost effectiveness across many European countries is mandatory. **If the case for lighting interventions is to be well made, then these economic concerns cannot be ignored.**

Assess the Costs of Inaction

A first critical step is to **identify the potential costs associated with not taking action to improve access to good light exposure**. Inaction is not cost free; many data are available on the costs to health care systems and society of living with different conditions, such as depression or anxiety. Information on both short and longer terms costs of these conditions can be collated, and the potential economic benefits of even a small reduction in risk calculated.

Provide Clear Cost and Resource Estimates

It is also essential to **present policy makers with basic information on the resources needed and costs of any lighting intervention**. This should include resources and costs for any design and development costs (for instance for outdoor lighting installations), as well as the costs of installation, energy use and maintenance. This will help in determining the budgetary impact of any intervention; it may also help dispel misperceptions about cost.

Consider Benefits not only Cost Savings

For a lighting intervention to have a good economic case, it should be stressed that it does not need to 'save money'. Many policy actions, certainly in health sector, will increase costs but at the same time improve outcomes. **Different methods of economic evaluation can be used to compare the relative costs and benefits of two or more policy choices**. The two most useful are cost benefit analysis and cost utility analysis.

Conduct Cost-Benefit Analysis to Align Funding Priorities

When the potential funders of a lighting intervention are **outside of the health sector we would recommend conducting a cost benefit analysis**. This puts a monetary value on all the benefits of an intervention, e.g. the economic value of a good night's sleep, reduction in workplace absenteeism etc and compares these with implementation costs. It is important in this evaluation to **include impacts that are of most relevance to potential funders**, e.g. if a lighting intervention is to be funded from a tourism related budget then impacts on retail trade and perceptions of crime may be very important. If benefits outweigh costs then the intervention is considered to be a good investment.

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Conduct Cost-Utility Analysis

If an economic case for lighting interventions is made **within the health system, we would recommend a cost-utility analysis** where **quality of life** is measured. This is the preferred primary outcome measure for economic evaluations in the health system. Decision makers compare improvements in quality of life relative to their costs and changes in the use of health and social care services; choosing quality of life as the outcome measure means that very different interventions, e.g. lighting interventions and antidepressants can be directly compared in health economic studies.

Build Decision Models on the Cost-Effectiveness

Currently there is very limited evidence on the cost effectiveness of different indoor and outdoor lighting interventions. One further way to increase the evidence base

is to work with economists to build decision models to estimate the potential economic case of investment. This approach is widely used in health economics and brings together existing evidence on effectiveness of lighting interventions with information on their costs.

Use Modeling to Assess Cost-Effectiveness and Impact Uncertainty

Models can also be used vary assumptions, for instance on the costs of lighting interventions, whether the target population, e.g. older people, make use of interventions as intended, and/or on the level and duration of effect. This means models can look at whether lighting interventions continue to have a good economic case even if their benefits are much lower than anticipated, and/or their costs much higher. This can increase the confidence of potential funders that good lighting is a good investment.

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